

Supplementary Material

From Topology to Time: Predicting Circadian Gene Oscillation via Deep Graph Networks

1 Complete list of TEDs

Table 1: Dataset Quality Index (DQI) for all 151 temporal expression datasets. Bold rows indicate valid datasets ($Q \geq 0.45$). Dataset names without the `.tsv` extension.

Dataset	Q	Dataset	Q
Mouse_Adrenal_Gland	0.84	paola_cdkl5_hippo_WT	0.58
circadian_atlas_Liv	0.81	mouse_NCK_ken	0.58
Mouse_Liver_48hr	0.81	mouse_night_feeding_WT	0.58
circadian_atlas_Lun	0.78	Mouse_3T3_48hr	0.58
GSE70499_WT	0.78	circadian_atlas_Bstm	0.58
Mouse_SCN_WT	0.77	New_Liver_RE_AL_RE	0.58
Mouse_Liver_WT_sassone_illumina	0.77	RE_WT_tomoki	0.58
kidney_NO	0.76	aging_epidermal_young	0.58
circadian_atlas_Hrt	0.76	ec_ko_guan	0.57
circadian_atlas_BFat	0.75	mouse_morning_sedentary_transcriptome	0.57
MEF_Dznep	0.75	GSE70499_KO	0.56
circadian_atlas_Mus	0.75	paola_cdkl5_hippo_KO	0.54
MEF_DMSO	0.74	SKE_EXP	0.54
circadian_atlas_Kid	0.74	aging_epidermal_aged	0.54
Mouse_Kidney_CCD	0.73	kc_wt_guan	0.53
aging_epidermal_high_fat	0.73	mouse_morning_run_transcriptome	0.52
circadian_atlas_Hyp	0.73	ec_wt_guan	0.52
mouse_fetal_kidney_wt_dan	0.72	ko_tomoki	0.50
circadian_atlas_Adr	0.71	GSE287759_female_IgG	0.50
liver_NO	0.71	rpf_wt_guan	0.50
aging_satellite_adult_restricted_diet	0.71	mouse_liver_petrus_RE	0.50
aging_epidermal_ND_control_diet	0.71	mouse_scn_high_fat	0.50
kidney_IH	0.71	pregnancy_OCH	0.50
Mouse_Kidney_DCT	0.71	pregnancy_OPH	0.48
aging_epidermal_adult_restricted_diet	0.70	pregnancy_OCL	0.47
MOUSE_SCN_SALINE	0.70	mouse_scn_control	0.47
scn_control_light	0.69	New_Liver_RE_TRF_KO	0.46
circadian_atlas_Aor	0.69	ncr_moisan	0.46
aging_satellite_aged_control_diet	0.69	pregnancy_C	0.46

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Table 1 continued

Dataset	Q	Dataset	Q
Mouse_Macrophages_DD	0.69	RE_tomoki	0.46
circadian_atlas_WFat	0.68	paola_cdkl5_scn_WT	0.46
sirt1_WT	0.67	kc_ko_guan	0.46
sirt1_KO	0.67	Mouse_Breast_WT	0.45
heart_IH	0.67	scn_control_dark	0.44
aging_epidermal_control_diet	0.67	paola_cdkl5_scn_KO	0.44
circadian_atlas_Cer	0.67	fasting_liver_fs	0.43
aging_epidermal_restricted_diet	0.66	fasting_muscle_fs	0.43
Mouse_Pituitary	0.66	liver_control_dark	0.43
aging_satellite_aged_restricted_diet	0.66	scn_tryptophan_dark	0.42
mouse_HFK_ken	0.66	pregnancy_OPL	0.41
liver_cell_2013_hf	0.66	Mouse_Liver_KO_sassone_illumina	0.39
mouse_liver_petrus_WT	0.66	hfr_moisan	0.38
adlib_ko_guan	0.66	total_ko_tomoki	0.38
liver_cell_2013_nc	0.66	GSE287759_male_antibody	0.38
mouse_evening_run_transcriptome	0.66	Mouse_Liver_WT	0.38
New_Liver_RE_TRF_RE	0.65	fasting_muscle_nc	0.37
aging_satellite_adult_control_diet	0.65	GSE288858_female_light_dark	0.34
mouse_night_feeding_KO	0.65	liver_tryptophan_light	0.34
heart_NO	0.64	liver_tryptophan_dark	0.34
aging_satellite_high_fat	0.63	New_Liver_RE_AL_KO	0.34
liver_IH	0.63	mouse_liver_petrus_KO	0.34
aging_satellite_control_diet	0.63	GSE287759_male_IgG	0.34
New_Liver_RE_TRF_WT	0.63	pregnancy_PF	0.34
sirt6_WT	0.62	Mouse_Muscle_WT	0.32
New_Liver_RE_AL_WT	0.62	mouse_liver_mus_mus_LMRE	0.31
mouse_liver_mus_liver_LMRE	0.62	GSE284053_Female	0.30
Liver_Terajima_KO	0.62	GSE287818_pyramidal_cells_female	0.30
adlib_wt_guan	0.62	GSE284601_WT_condition	0.30
ethanol_chronic_control	0.62	GSE284601_LKO_condition	0.30
Mouse_Distal_Colon	0.62	GSE297702_female_WT_WT	0.30
ethanol_chronic_etoh	0.62	GSE284601_F_condition	0.30
mouse_liver_mus_mus_WT_Dub	0.62	GSE284053_Male	0.30
sirt6_KO	0.62	GSE284601_KO_condition	0.30
Mouse_Liver_RE_sassone_illumina	0.62	scn_tryptophan_light	0.30
fasting_liver_nc	0.61	GSE287759_female_antibody	0.30
mouse_evening_sedentary_transcriptome	0.61	nc_moisan	0.30
liver_control_light	0.61	GSE297702_male_WT_WT	0.30
Mouse_Liver_Panda	0.61	kristin_ko_09_2022	0.30
SKE_WT	0.60	kristin_wt_09_2022	0.30
MOUSE_SCN_DZnep	0.60	GSE287818_pyramidal_cells_male	0.30
aging_epidermal_adult_control_diet	0.60	pregnancy_CF	0.27
rpf_ko_guan	0.59	hf_moisan	0.15

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Table 1 continued

Dataset	Q	Dataset	Q
Mouse_Aorta	0.58	pregnancy_P	0.15
mouse_liver_mus_liver_WT_Dub	0.58	GSE287818_parvalbumin_female	0.15
Liver_Terajima_WT	0.58	GSE287818_parvalbumin_male	0.15
wt_tomoki	0.58		

2 Hyperparameters search spaces

Table 2. Grid searches hyperparameters.

Hyperparameter	applies to	values
Hidden dim	All	64, 128, 512
Layers	All	1,2,4,8,16
Convolutional operator	GCN	GraphConv, GIN, DirGNNConv
ϕ layers	DeepSets, DeepSetsConv	1,2,4
Unknown node init.	All	0, 0.5, neighbor_mean
Learning rate	All	1e-3, 5e-4
Dropout p	All	0.25
Batch size	All	512